

LEGAL BASIS FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF INSURANCE ACTIVITIES

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Abstract: In society, citizens and their community have an appropriate social relationship with each other in the process of their activities. To put these relationships in one mold, it is necessary to put them in order, that is, to define the framework of action of citizens and organizations. What is stated also applies to insurance up to payment. Insurance as a socio-economic law requires strengthening from the legal side. The relationship that arises in the process of establishing and using an insurance fund is legally regulated.

Keywords: socio-economic development, contractual obligations, civil-legal relations.

Legal relations that arise in the insurance industry are part of civil-legal relations. Such relations regulate the legal status of participants in civil circulation, property rights and other material rights, contractual obligations, as well as property and personal non-property relations.

Civil-legal relations in the field of insurance are manifested in the following areas:

- * civil-legal relations formed between citizens and insurance organizations;
- * interaction between insurance organizations;
- * civil-legal relations that arise between citizens and special state bodies;
- * civil-legal relations that arise between insurance organizations and a specially authorized state body.

The civil-legal relationship that arises between citizens and insurance organizations is based on the provisions of the corresponding contract. In this, on

the one hand, the duty and obligations of the insurance organization to the citizen appear before the Citizen, on the other hand, to the insurance organization of the citizen. That is, according to the concluded contract, a citizen must pay an insurance premium on time. In the event of an insured event, the insurance organization must pay the citizen the insurance cover (sum) in the terms and conditions recorded in the insurance contract. It turns out that the contract –as a civil law document-is legally regulating the interaction of the parties.

Civil-legal relations of insurance organizations that arise between each other are formed within the framework of concluded contracts related to insurance money and reinsurance. According to current legislation, an insurance organization can participate in insurance money or enter into contractual relations with other insurance organizations or specialized reinsurance organizations in order to ensure financial stability, consequently, to ensure its fulfillment in the face of insurers. Article 959 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan specifically states that "the risk of paying the insurance compensation or insurance money that the insurer assumes under the insurance contract can be insured by him in full or in part under another insurer (insurers) under the reinsurance contract concluded with him".

In relation to the reinsurance contract, if the reinsurance contract does not provide for a different procedure, the provisions of the civil code that must be applied to the insurance of entrepreneurial risk apply. Under the insurance contract (basic contract) that establishes the reinsurance contract, the insurer is the insurer in the next contract.

The civil-legal relationship that arises between citizens and special state bodies is associated with the protection of the legitimate interests of citizens – who are insurers of a specially authorized state body. In practice, there are cases in which an insurance organization can unreasonably give up the insurance coverage of the damages incurred by the insured due to the insured event. In order to legally protect their interests at such a time, the insurer can apply to a specially authorized state body.

Civil-legal relations that arise between insurance organizations and a specially authorized state body are regulated on the basis of legislation. The civil-legal relations of the specially authorized body that arise in relation to insurance organizations are reflected in the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the law on "insurance activities". A specially authorized state body oversees the activities of insurance organizations in the manner prescribed by law. And if necessary, he has the right to recall a license that gives him the right to carry out insurance activities in order to protect the interests of insurers.

In the following cases, the types of life insurance that apply for a period of more than one year, providing for the obligations of the insurer on the payment of insurance amounts, the total:

- the life of the insured until the end of the insurance period or until the age specified in the insurance contract;

- death of the insured;

also current payments (annuities) during the validity of the insurance contract, except for Class III

Provided that the specified insurance period is established for a period of not less than five years or until the insured reaches retirement age, a total of life insurance types that ensure that insurance amounts are paid in case of an accident or a certain type of accident or loss of employment as a result of severe injury due to illness or illness. In this case, the insurance period specified in the contract cannot be unilaterally terminated or changed by the insurer.

In the following cases:

- a) when the insurer suffers a loss as a result of interruption of the insurer's business (economic activity) or a decrease in the scale of the business (economic activity) carried out by the insurer;

(b) when the insurer suffers losses as a result of costs not foreseen (except as specified in class 17;

C) the total of the types of insurance that ensure the payment of insurance coverage in the event of losses other than those specified in paragraphs (A) and (b) of this level as a result of the implementation of activities related to the structure and implementation of contracts

The legal regulation of insurance is carried out by the state through the means of legal norms of the act of participants in the connection of insurance. There are social relations that arise in the process of insurance activities carried out at the expense of a special fund, which is established by most individuals in order to provide various unpredictable insured protection of the property rights of individuals and legal entities. The sum of the norms that regulate this relationship is called insurance law.

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